

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram

Maps of linear settlements and their 15 minute catchment areas in Vienna

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emc2 - WP3

The deliverable describes a morphological analysis of Vienna's peripheral linear settlements and shows their development since ca. 1820. The morphogenetic study is based on the vectorization of historic maps and orthophotos (with highlighted historic buildings). It provides an understanding of the ways and extents to which the historic villages were transformed and adapted while becoming part of the fabric of the growing city (urbanisation process).

The study presented here covers ten selected villages (linear settlement structures) in the urban area of Vienna—on the fringe of the city—which were examined in six different time-frames. These villages were selected in a two-step process. Out of 131 villages (in and around Vienna) 26 were examined in an initial approach. On the basis of this analysis, a catalogue of criteria was drawn up in a second step to further narrow down the selection and thus determine the ten suitable examples. The criteria for the selection and the selection process are described in detail in the following chapter.

In order to be able to carry out comparative analyses as accurately as possible, the various historical plans were vectorised using CAD software. Subsequently, overlay methods were used to show the respective changes. In this way, visualisations were created in a morphogenetic approach that do represent the diverse conversion and urbanisation processes of the originally rural villages.

Original Source Data

In order to trace the morphological development of linear settlements, the following sources provided the data basis for vectorisation:

- ~1820 Franziszeischer Kataster (Franciscan Cadastre)
<https://maps.arcanum.com/de/map/cadastral/>
- 1870s Franzisko-Josephinische Landesaufnahme (Third land Survey)
<https://maps.arcanum.com/de/map/europe-19century-thirdsurvey/>
- 1912 Generalstadtplan (General City Plan of Vienna)
https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/dataset/stadt-wien_generalstadtplan1912wien
- 1938 Aerial Photograph
<https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/dataset/b411c576-e81b-490b-9c5b-8ef36f4f542d>
- 1971 Aerial Photograph
<https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/dataset/luftbildplan-1971-wien>
<https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/dataset/luftbildplan-1971-umland-wien>
- 2020s Map of Status Quo
<https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

Selection of Settlements

For the topic-specific morphological analysis the current political boundaries must not be seen as a-priori relevant, as, to a certain extent, they do represent a variable: city boundaries have changed considerably over the period under consideration. Thus, for the Vienna-specific analysis of the historical settlement form 'Straßendorf' (linear settlement), a relevant observation area was therefore determined: a radius of 30 km was drawn from the geographical centre of the city.

In this area, 131 villages were counted that—corresponding to a previously determined catalogue of criteria—must be considered linear settlements of a certain order.

Urban settlements in central locations that were completely absorbed and overwritten by the historical grid city of the 19th century were left out, because 1) the actual urbanisation process can no longer be conclusively traced here and because, furthermore, 2) they fall outside the scope of the EMC2 study, which focuses on the urban fringe.

A large proportion of the villages identified in this way are located outside the current city limits; only 30 are located within. Of these 30, 19 were taken to the next phase of analysis (vectorisation).

Ultimately, the aim of this study is to understand urbanisation processes by analysing network-relevant linear structures and to gain insights into the development of a sustainable system for the urban fringe.

In line with the focus set by the overarching EMC2 research project the objective therefore is not a neat categorisation of linear settlement structures, but rather an understanding of urbanisation processes and an assessment of how urban sub-centres develop or disappear and, ultimately, what factors are relevant for a future-fit urban structure.

For these analytical reasons, the number of villages to be examined was increased in a next step by nine villages. Although these were not technically catalogue-compliant linear villages, they were included for reasons of workability and comparability.

So, of all the linear settlements identified in Vienna, 26 villages were ultimately chosen for vectorisation. And this is where the project—in parallel with further research—transitioned into research-led teaching: During three semesters (between October 2023 and January 2025), the selected villages were addressed by a total of 78 students as part of a historical-analytical and an urban-planning assignment.

The task was to process the structures based on existing historical planning data, which in itself presented a first problem: since some of the villages were located outside the former city limits (two major city expansions took place in 1850 and 1890) and since the historical Generalstadtplan only covered the city area of Vienna that was valid at the time, the data situation proved to be extraordinarily challenging in some cases.

After this first vectorisation step—and after the researchers themselves had revised the results accordingly—three respectively four time frames were available for each settlement. Based on these initial results, ten of the villages were then selected for a further in-depth analysis.

For this shortlist, resources were pooled to conduct further research and to elaborate the plans for further time frames. After this processing step, six respectively five time frames per settlement were ultimately available for the morphogenetic analysis.

The ten settlements were selected according to three main characteristics:

1. Extend of change within the village structure as a result of urbanisation processes (transformation in relation to the remaining buildings and preservation of historical street layout)
2. Status with regard to the configurational parameters (relationship with the main street, urban integration and environment)
3. Topography (geographic and hydrographic location: in valleys, on hillsides or flat areas and near or far from watercourses)

In the selection process, particular attention was paid to ensuring that the entire range and various combinations of these characteristics are represented. The selected settlements and their respective defining characteristics are:

Großjedlersdorf

- limited transformation in an encapsulated settlement centre, unchanged original historical street layout
- medium urban integration, parallel to main street, patchwork environment
- no significant topography and no waterbody

Oberlaa

- limited transformation, unchanged original historical street layout
- no relevant main streets close, limited urban integration, party still rural environment
- moderate valley, parallel to a stream

Leopoldau

- limited transformation in encapsulated settlement centre, unchanged original historical street layout
- main streets surrounding, high urban integration, patchwork environment
- no significant topography and no waterbody

Untersievering

- medium transformation, unchanged original historical street layout
- on main street, medium urban integration, party still rural environment
- in a valley alongside a stream

Penzing

- medium transformation, unchanged original historical street layout
- main streets surrounding, high urban integration, consolidated urban environment
- moderate hillside, parallel to a river

Mauer

- medium transformation, unchanged original historical street layout
- on two main streets, medium urban integration, scattered settlement environment
- aligned along the slope/perpendicular to the hillside, historical streams now channelled

Inzersdorf

- significant transformation, nearly unchanged original historical street layout
- perpendicular to main street, medium urban integration, patchwork environment
- moderate valley, parallel to a stream

Stadlau

- significant transformation, partly unchanged original historical street layout
- no relevant main streets close, medium urban integration, patchwork environment
- no significant topography, historically strong relationship with the Danube

Simmering

- significant transformation, but unchanged historical street layout
- diagonal to a main street, high urban integration, consolidated urban environment
- moderate hillside, historically strong relationship with the Danube

Ottakring

- most significant transformation, considerably changed historical street layout
- main streets surrounding in a grid, high urban integration, consolidated urban environment
- moderate valley, historical stream now channelled

Process

As mentioned above, a significant part of this work was carried out as part of research-led teaching in collaboration with students at the TU Wien. Over a period of three semesters, students from three different courses worked on the linear settlement structures in Vienna. An integral component of the students' work involved the two-dimensional vectorisation of the assigned linear settlement, utilising historical maps from the 19th and 20th century in three historical states. In a subsequent phase, the students compared their historical results with the current situation in order to illustrate how these linear settlement structures, with their characteristic types of farmsteads, have developed morphogenetically. The historical maps created by the students provide a visual representation of the situation in the 1820s, 1870s and 1910s. To incorporate spatial developments from the 20th century, vectorized orthophotos were created by the team of TUW from 1938 and 1971.

Another significant step was to define the research area in and around the linear settlement structure. This was accomplished through the delineation of a 15-minute catchment area, utilising the demo-version of the Travel Time Map. The respective catchment area is a merge of three individual catchment areas based on points set in the centre of the village and at both ends. The catchment radius is understood to refer to the current situation, and was also adopted in this form for the historical conditions.

Within each time frame, it was necessary to classify whether the building footprints of the respective buildings within the linear settlement structure corresponded to one of the original characteristic farmstead types (marked in red). Additionally, relevant historical objects within the settlement core, such as churches or clearly recognizable older building structures that had survived over time, are marked in red. Newer buildings within the structure or the developing environment are displayed in grey. The graphics represent a preliminary approach to the task; individual buildings may differ or, in the case of coarser differences and distortions within historical map material, positionings and the like always had to be decided based on the situation.

Historical Maps and Present Situation

The starting point for the students was the Franziszeische Kataster from ca. 1820. This was followed by the vectorization of the Franzisco-Josephinische Landesaufnahme (1870s). It was noted that until the close of the 19th century, a growth process with the historical characteristic and agriculturally influenced building layouts was observable, particularly in more peripheral villages. However, the third time frame, the Generalstadtplan of 1912, demonstrates a constant urbanisation, and henceforth, a constant reduction of the historic farmstead buildings.

The students further categorised the present building stock according to whether or not the buildings correspond to the historic farmstead types (marked in red). In this assessment, a novel conversion category was introduced and annotated in red. In the latter half of the 20th century and the 21st century, several historical farmstead types, which were originally only single-storey high, were given an additional floor. Despite this development, the historical substance of the buildings is still clearly recognisable. Subsequent to the submission of the students' plans, a review was conducted by the supervisors, with the objective of identifying and rectifying any significant errors.

Orthophotos

The components for the vectorization of the orthophotos followed the current plan and the orthophotos of the city of Vienna from 1938 and 1971, which are available online as OGD. The approach undertaken by TUW was to work backwards through time, starting with the current state and comparing it with the aerial photograph of 1971. The condition of the surrounding buildings was adapted, and the identification of further historical single-storey farmstead types was examined. In addition to the visual recognition of corresponding historical building layouts, the shadows cast in the aerial view often provided insights into the number of storeys. Utilising the basis of 1971, the same methodical approach was employed to investigate the condition of the buildings in the 1938 orthophoto. In instances where the image resolution proved inadequate, critical cases were not displayed within the building context, or if they could not be clearly identified as a historic farmstead type, they were not marked in red.

Conclusio

The selection of the ten villages examined offers a representative range of examples of the historical settlement structure on the outskirts of Vienna. On the one hand, there are villages that were almost completely transformed, i.e. have almost entirely 'disappeared' in their original form, such as Ottakring or Simmering. On the other hand, there are linear settlements such as Leopoldau or Oberlaa, which have retained their village character with a large number of historic buildings and farmstead types. A closer look at the three characteristics outlined above in the list of villages reveals that no clear patterns can be identified, and that only a few similarities between the individual linear settlement structures can be found. Instead, these ten villages, selected for their representativeness, illustrate the intricate interplay of the influencing factors and parameters that have shaped the linear settlement structures over time, leading to their spatial transformation and the characteristics they display in the present. One notable observation is that villages exhibiting a „medium“ or „significant“ transformation are predominantly characterised by high integration, or at the very least, medium integration. The significance of the location of the main streets as an indicator for the degree of transformation and change within the building structure appears to be a relevant factor. Exciting cross-references and correlations to the diachronic analysis of SMOG can already be established here, which are overlaid and examined in more detail in following contributions.

Disclaimer

Despite the associated margin of uncertainty, these approaches and methodologies provide a useful approximation for reflecting the morphogenesis of selected spatial structures, in this case linear settlement structures. The size of the research area selected and the methods chosen mean that the accuracy of the work is not expressed at the plot level, but at scales above it.

Links:

<https://app.traveltime.com/>

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D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Großjedlersdorf
1821

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Großjedlersdorf
1875

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Großjedlersdorf
1912

Großjedlersdorf 1938

Light grey: area not included in Orthophoto 1938,
footprints based on Orthophoto 1971

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Großjedlersdorf
1971

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Großjedlersdorf
2020s

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Inzersdorf
1818

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Inzersdorf
1875

Inzersdorf
1912

No Data available,
Area not included in Generalstadtplan

Inzersdorf
1938

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Inzersdorf
1971

Inzersdorf
2020s

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Oberlaa
1818

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Oberlaa
1875

Oberlaa
1912

No Data available,
Area not included in Generalstadtplan

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Oberlaa
1938

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Oberlaa
1971

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Oberlaa
2020s

Leopoldau
1821

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Leopoldau
1875

Leopoldau
1912

Leopoldau
1938

Leopoldau
1971

Leopoldau
2020s

Mauer
1819

Mauer
1875

Mauer
1912

No Data available,
Area not included in Generalstadtplan

Mauer
1938

Mauer
1971

Mauer
2020s

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Ottakring
1819

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Ottakring
1875

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Ottakring
1912

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Ottakring
1938

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Ottakring
1971

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Ottakring
2020s

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Penzing
1819

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Penzing
1875

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Penzing
1912

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Penzing
1938

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Penzing
1971

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Penzing
2020s

Simmering
1818

Simmering
1875

Simmering
1912

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Simmering
1938

Light grey: area not included in Orthophoto 1938,
footprints based on Orthophoto 1971

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Simmering
1971

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Simmering
2020s

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Stadlau
1820-1821

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Stadlau
1875

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Stadlau
1912

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Stadlau
1938

Light grey: area not included in Orthophoto 1938,
footprints based on Orthophoto 1971

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Stadlau
1971

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Stadlau
2020s

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Untersievering
1819

Untersievering
1875

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Untersievering
1912

Untersievering
1938

D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas

Untersievering
1971

Untersievering
2020s

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WP3 - D3.2 Morphogenetic diagram
Maps of the chosen test areas

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Urbanisme

